

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

BASIC TUTORIAL *RISIS CIB2*

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1 Basic Characteristics

The Corporate Invention Board (CIB2) database is designed for the analysis of technological knowledge creation of the worldwide top corporate R&D performers, using patents as a proxy. It focuses on the 'priority patents'¹ applied by the parent companies and the subsidiaries they control. CIB2 includes the patent applications of 3992 companies. For patents, it relies on the patent data included in the RISIS Patent Database (RPD)². The list of companies was elaborated using several editions of the EU Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard and the lists of WIPO top applicants.

The RISIS CIB2 database provides on the one hand essential patent information organised in 6 tables, for analysing the geography and the actors of the knowledge production, the content and the value of the knowledge production. It also gives basic data on the parent companies (locations, sectors, size, financial data, employees) in 5 additional tables.

The RISIS CIB2 database is designed as a user-friendly relational database using a Mysql querying environment. This basic tutorial provides condensed user-oriented information on the content of the RISIS Patent database for different kinds of research questions. It provides an overview on the main tables and data. For all technical details of the database refer to the RISIS CIB2 technical documentation (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/4/metadata>).

2 Data base content

The RISIS CIB2 database uses the RISIS Patent database, a LISIS enriched and simplified version of the PATSTAT 2017 April release, as a primary source. It covers priority patent applications worldwide, i.e. at all regional and national offices in the world.

CIB2 includes the 6,158,064 priority patents of invention applied by 3992 parent companies (and their consolidated subsidiaries) from 2000 to 2015, (patents applied in 2015 are not all included). The patents include 15,712,409 inventors³.

The global data model is shown in figure 1.

¹ A priority patent is the first patent application to protect a new invention. It represents the creation of new knowledge

² For an extensive description of the RPD, see the Risis Patent Database documentation

https://zenodo.org/record/3342454/files/Documentation_RISIS%20Patstat_Final.pdf?download=1

³ Corresponding to 3,632,109 distinct person_id

Figure 1: The data model of the CIB2 database

The patent variables⁴ give information related to:

- Legal information on the application such as the date of the filing and the office where the patent was first filed
- **The content of the invention, using textual pieces of information** such as the patent titles, the patent abstracts and a text concatenating the definitions of the patent IPC (International Patent Classification) codes. Based on the definition of some **75000 IPC classes** provided for by PATSTAT, the latter builds a rich vocabulary enriching the content available for semantic analyses.
- **The technological content using the standard technology classification:** (IPC subclasses, aggregation of IPC codes) by technological domains, fields or subfields. Patent allocation in the different classifications is realised on a fractional count basis according to their IPC classes.
- **The geographical location of inventive activities.** As we are interested in the geography of knowledge creation, we focus on inventors' addresses (instead of using applicants' addresses which would more capture commercialisation). Their addresses, their geocoded coordinates as well as the allocation of their addresses to geographical areas are given.
- **The legal organisations that apply for patents (the applicants).** For each patent, at least one applicant is a legal entity belonging to a parent company. In case of co-application, the names of other legal co-applicants are given. Their addresses, their geocoded coordinates as well as the allocation of their addresses to geographical areas are given.
- **Characteristics linked to the 'value' of the patent:** was the patent granted or not, the size of patent families, the presence in 5 world-level patent offices (EPO, USPTO, Japan Patent Office, Korean Patent Office, China Patent Office) and citations they have received.

The firm variables⁵ give information related to:

⁴ Details on the patent variables are given on https://zenodo.org/record/3342454/files/Documentation_RISIS%20Patstat_Final.pdf?download=1

⁵ Details on the patent variables are given on https://zenodo.org/record/3342454/files/Documentation_RISIS%20Patstat_Final.pdf?download=1

- The company names (GUO or iGUO) including a current name but also previous and alternative company names
- A set of legal information of the company like its date of incorporation; Is it an active firm? Is it a quoted firm? Is it a GUO or an iGUO?
- The geographical location of the headquarter of the company including the address, city, country, latitude, longitude, NUTS3 regions and the functional area name (also named URA for Urban or Rural Area) and ID
- The industrial sectors of the company using NACE2 codes and labels (primary and secondary NACE codes)
- Some economic and financial data of the company including number of employees, turnover, assets, R&D investments, Profit/loss, ROE, ROA. Financial data are given for the most recent available years (up to ten years depending on the data availability).

3 Key figures

The diversity of the 3992 top R&D companies present in CIB2, both in terms of industrial sector and geography (location of the parent company HQ) is presented in the two following tables.

Table 1: Industrial sectors of the parent companies included in CIB2

Sector of the parent companies NACE 2 (4 digits)	Number of parent companies	Share of parent companies
Manufacture of pharmaceutical preparations	309	7,70%
Manufacture of electronic components	284	7,10%
Other software publishing	136	3,40%
Activities of head offices	111	2,80%
Computer programming activities	111	2,80%
Manufacture of communication equipment	98	2,50%
Activities of holding companies	96	2,40%
Manufacture of other special-purpose machinery	93	2,30%
Manufacture of instruments and appliances for measuring, testing and navigation	89	2,20%
Manufacture of medical and dental instruments and supplies	86	2,20%
Manufacture of other parts and accessories for motor vehicles	84	2,10%
Manufacture of computers and peripheral equipment	81	2,00%
Manufacture of other chemical products nec	77	1,90%
Research and experimental development on biotechnology	68	1,70%
Other information technology and computer service activities	67	1,70%
Other telecommunications activities	66	1,70%
Manufacture of motor vehicles	51	1,30%
Unknown	48	1,20%
Production of electricity	40	1,00%

Total	3992	100%
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Table 2: Geographical location of the headquarters of the parent companies included in CIB2

Country of headquarter	Number of parent companies	Share of parent companies	Cumulated share of parent companies
US	1067	26,80%	26,80%
JP	558	14,00%	40,70%
DE	330	8,20%	49,00%
GB	316	7,90%	56,90%
CN	268	6,70%	63,60%
FR	156	3,90%	67,50%
KR	143	3,60%	71,10%
TW	106	2,70%	73,70%
SE	107	2,70%	76,40%
IT	83	2,10%	78,50%
NL	76	1,90%	80,40%
CH	71	1,80%	82,20%
KY	69	1,80%	83,90%
FI	62	1,60%	85,50%
IN	59	1,50%	87,00%
AT	54	1,40%	88,30%
DK	53	1,30%	89,70%
CA	56	1,40%	91,10%
BE	47	1,20%	92,20%
ES	31	0,80%	93,00%
IL	31	0,80%	93,80%
Total	3992		100%

Number of patents over time

The RISIS Patent database includes all the priority patents of invention applied for by the top corporate R&D performers from 2000 to 2015, i.e. 6,158,064 patent applications (Figure 2). The evolution of the number of patent applications over time in CIB2 as well as the ratio of the number of CIB2 patents/number of patents in RISIS Patent Database are shown below (patents applied in 2015 are not all included in the database). The figures show that the number of CIB2 patents over time increases but not as fast as the number of overall patents in RISIS Patent Database.

Figure 2: Number of priority patents in CIB2 and share of CIB2 in Risis Patent database

Geography of the inventions

In 93% of the patents, the location of the inventions (inventors' geographical location) is known and in 97.7% of them, the location of the applicant is indicated. The ten first countries of inventions (inventors' addresses) and applicants when including all priority patents of CIB2 are shown in table 3 and table 4. The dominance of Asian countries is straightforward. It becomes less and less visible when selecting only IP5 family patents, triadic patents and IP5 patents.

Table 3: Distribution of patent inventors by country

Country of inventors	Number of patent applications with an inventor from the country	Share of patent applications with an inventor from the country
Total number of priority patents	6,158,064	
JP	3,050,764	49,50%
US	932,996	15,20%
KR	607,495	9,90%
DE	464,67	7,50%
Unknown	430,703	7,00%
CN	421,493	6,80%
TW	139,289	2,30%
FR	133,642	2,20%
GB	66,77	1,10%
CA	45,642	0,70%
NL	41,424	0,70%

Table 4: Distribution of patent applicants by country

Country of applicant	Number of patents with applicant from the country	Share of patents with applicant from the country
Total number of priority patents	6,158,064	
JP	3,064,415	49,80%
US	946,49	15,40%
KR	622,967	10,10%
DE	419,248	6,80%
CN	333,244	5,40%
TW	144,741	2,40%
Unknown	138,904	2,30%
FR	122,298	2,00%
GB	60,423	1,00%
NL	51,827	0,80%
SE	48,719	0,80%

Typology of actors

We deal with actors that are companies among the top worldwide R&D performers (either because, they have the highest R&D investments or because they apply for a large number of PCT patents). In addition to the 3992 top R&D corporate applicants, the database includes the names and geocoded addresses of the co-applicants when the patents are co-applications. Co-applicants are either other companies, entities from the public sector, NGOs,...

Basic statistics describing the patenting activities of the 3992 CIB2 companies are shown in table 5. It shows a huge heterogeneity of the patenting activities of CIB2 companies.

Table 5: Distribution of companies in quartiles according to the number of patent applications

Statistics (3992 companies)	Number of priority patents
Minimum	0
Maximum	154,976
1st quartile	30
2 nd quartile	125
3 rd quartile	524
Mean	1,548

The distributions of the geography of **companies** (**company**' HQ) in the four quartiles are quite heterogeneous. The shares of the US and European **companies** dominate in the lower quartiles. In the 4th quartile, JP **companies** dominate.

The companies with the largest number of priority patent applications are shown below considering several types of patents: all the priority patents, IP5 family patents and IP5 priority patents⁶. The graphs give the patent share of a given company, i.e. its number of patents divided by the total number of patents in CIB2 (Figures 3 to 5).

The Asian companies dominate when considering all priority patent applications. When considering only the patent applied in the main worldwide IP offices (either one of the IP5 patent offices) or all of them), the number of large companies from western countries in the top corporate applicants significantly increases.

⁶ An IP5 family patent is a priority patent that is extended in at least a second country and for which one patent in the family was applied in one of the 5 largest IP offices (EPO, USPTO, KIPO, SINO) ; an IP5 patent is a priority patent for which the family includes applications in all the 5 largest IP offices.

Figure 3: Shares of the patent applications of the companies with the largest number of patent applications including all priority patent applications from 2000 to 2016.

Figure 4: Shares of the patent applications of the companies with the largest number of patent applications considering only IP5 family priority patent applications from 2000 to 2016

Figure 5: Shares of the patent applications of the companies with the largest number of patent applications considering only IP5 priority patent applications from 2000 to 2016

4 Querying the database

Currently, MySQL Workbench is used to deliver visual tools for creating, executing, and optimizing SQL queries. For the time being, querying the database, which requires an on-site visit at UGE in Paris, is carried out with the researchers from LISIS in charge of the database.

5 Scientific use and main references

RISIS CIB2 is an accessible and rich data source via RISIS for research activities in the production of knowledge using patent data. It allows studying the dynamics of knowledge creation in large and top corporate R&D performers along different dimensions: space, actors and technologies.

Thanks to its links with other RISIS facilities, RISIS CIB2 database enables to access these dimensions at a coarse level or at a fine grained level using either usual classification (for technologies, geography) or designing ad-hoc data subsets of patents in specific topics of inventions, for a particular type of institutions in given geographical spaces.

It had been recently used to:

- Study the worldwide trends of the R&D internationalisation in MNEs
- Analyse the commitment of MNEs in energy cleantech technologies

- Analyse the **exploitation of new knowledge** in specific industries (pharmaceutical and chemical industries), done by researchers from University Paris-Est Marne-la-Vallee
- Explore the **Inventive Productivity of Multinational Firms** using non parametric modelling (Conditional Efficiency Analysis)
- Characterise the R&D activities of top R&D corporate performers in the sectors of aeronautics, and aerospace

Recent References

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